

Evaluation of Complex and Computational Thinking in Higher Education: A Systematic Literature Mapping from 2014 to 2024

Research questions

Topics	Research questions	Possible answers
Geographical distribution of studies	RQ1 - What is the geographical distribution of studies on the assessment of complex thinking and computational thinking in university contexts?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Country origin • Cited times
Methodological design of the studies	RQ2 - What types of research, methodological approaches and designs are used in studies that assess complex and/or computational thinking in university contexts?	<p>RQ2. Study type:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Empirical • Theoretical/ Conceptual <p>RQ2a: Research type:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quantitative • Qualitative • Mixed method • Literature review <p>RQ2b. Research design:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quantitative: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Experimental design ○ Quasi-experimental designs ○ Pre-experimental ○ Ex-post-facto: transectional designs ○ Ex-post-facto: longitudinal designs. • Qualitative: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Narratives ○ Phenomenological studies ○ Grounded theory ○ Ethnographies ○ Case studies. • Mixed method: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Explanatory sequential design ○ Exploratory sequential design ○ Transformative sequential design ○ Concurrent triangulation design ○ Concurrent nested design. • Literature review: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Systematic Review ○ Scooping Review ○ Systematic Mapping Review ○ Meta-análisis ○ Umbrella review ○ Conceptual literature review/ Theoretical analysis <p>(Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017; Hernández Sampieri & Mendoza Torres, 2018; Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2008)</p>

<p>Evolution of scientific production</p>	<p>RQ3 - How has the academic production on the assessment of complex and/or computational thinking in university contexts evolved over time?</p>	<p>RQ3 – Publication year RQ3a – Type of thinking competence evaluated</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complex thinking • Computational thinking • Both
<p>University context of the study</p>	<p>RQ4 - What is the university academic context and disciplinary area of the study?</p>	<p>RQ4- Educational level</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Undergraduate university education • Postgraduate university education • Non-degree university programs (certificaciones, diplomados, cursos de capacitación). • Higher education in genera (General university student population, Mixed levels (undergraduate and graduate, Faculty development / university teacher training, Institutional or cross-program assessment models, University-wide platform or digital ecosystem evaluations) • Not specified <p>RQ4a – Disciplinary area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Teacher training ○ Educational sciences ○ Curriculum and pedagogy ○ Educational technology • Engineering and Technology <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Civil, mechanical, electrical, industrial engineering ○ Information and communication technologies ○ Robotics, automation, systems engineering • Computer Science / Informatics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Programming ○ Artificial intelligence ○ Software engineering ○ Data science • Health Sciences <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Medicine ○ Nursing ○ Public health ○ Dentistry ○ Physical therapy • Natural Sciences <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Physics

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Chemistry ○ Biology ○ Environmental sciences ○ Earth sciences ● Mathematics and Statistics ● Social Sciences ○ Psychology ○ Sociology ○ Anthropology ○ Political science ○ Communication studies ● Business and Management ○ Administration ○ Marketing ○ Finance ○ Human resources ○ Entrepreneurship ● Arts and Humanities ○ History ○ Philosophy ○ Literature ○ Arts, design, performing arts ○ Linguistics ● Law and Legal Studies ● Agricultural and Veterinary Sciences ● Multidisciplinary / Interdisciplinary ● Not specified <p>(UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2015)</p>
<p>Educational environments</p>	<p>RQ5 - ¿Qué tipo de entorno educativo o soporte tecnológico se utiliza en los estudios que abordan la evaluación del pensamiento complejo y/o computacional en contextos universitarios?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Learning Management System (LMS) - (Moodle, Blackboard) ● AI-based platforms or intelligent tutors ● Virtual or remote laboratories ● Gamified environments ● Coding environments / Computational tools - (Scratch, Python, Arduino, simulations) ● Digital learning platforms (non-LMS) - (Coursera, Khan Academy, Edmodo) ● Classroom-based ● Blended or hybrid models ● Online learning environments ● Not specified <p>(Li et al., 2024; Messer et al., 2024; Sajja et al., 2024; Sellberg et al., 2024; Simsek & Karakus Yilmaz, 2025).</p>

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